

Rapaloid

Adapting an Existing Framework for Emotional Speech Prosody Generation

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MASTER THESIS UPF/ 2012
Master in Sound and Music Computing

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Acknowledgments

This research project would not have been possible without the support of many people. First, I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. Xavier Serra for his confidence giving me the opportunity to join the SMC Master. I would also thank to the supervisor, Dr. Jordi Bonada, for his support, guidance and enthusiasm. Thanks to Martí Umbert and Merlijn Blaauw for their assistance, patience and fantastic scripts. Special thanks also to Neo for his disinterested help, you have provided us very good material for this project and for future work in the rap synthesis field. Many thanks as well to Catalunya Caixa Fellowship program for their confidence and their financial support during this year. I would also mention Enric Giné, who encouraged me to enrol this Master. Finally, I would like to thank my friends, family and girlfriend for their understanding and support.

Abstract

The aim of this project is to model a Spanish rap singer, applying the knowledge about emotional speech prosody to this musical style close to the speech. Pitch and duration are modelled using Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). The context features used in the HMM training will be adapted to the new scenario, taking into account the rhythmic constraints of the rap. From this trained model, performance trajectories will be generated for the Vocaloid synthesizer, allowing it to synthesize rap.

Contents

List of Figures	vii
List of Tables	viii
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Voice synthesis	1
1.2 Style modelling	2
1.3 Rap-style singing voice synthesis	3
2 RAP SYNTHESIS IN VOCALOID	4
2.1 Analysis	5
2.1.1 Recording and processing	5
2.1.2 Phonetic transcription and segmentation	5
2.1.3 Pitch extraction	6
2.2 Resynthesis	7
2.2.1 Vocaloid score	7
2.2.2 Phonetic alignment and note alignment	7
2.2.3 Results	8
3 MODELLING	9
3.1 Symbolic input and parameters	9
3.1.1 Input format	10
3.1.2 Label format	10
3.1.3 Label generation	10

3.2	HMM training	12
3.2.1	Tree-based clustering	13
3.3	Vocaloid score generation	14
4	RESULTS	15
4.1	Phonetic based model	15
4.2	Note based model	26
5	CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	48

List of Figures

1.1	Yamaha rap synthesis score	3
2.1	Neo during the recording session	4
2.2	Manual phonetic alignment in Wavesurfer	5
2.3	Pitch extraction in SMSTools	6
2.4	Vocaloid rap resynthesis process	7
3.1	Example of a flow diagram	9
3.2	Input symbolic representation	10
3.3	General view of the HTS system	12
3.4	Decision trees	13
4.1	phoneme based model, hts engine: pitch curves	16
4.2	phoneme based model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	17
4.3	phoneme based model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	18
4.4	phoneme based model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	19
4.5	phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves	20
4.6	phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves	21
4.7	phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves	22
4.8	phoneme based model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	23
4.9	phoneme based model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	24
4.10	phoneme based model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	25
4.11	note based model, hts engine: pitch curves	28
4.12	note based model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	29
4.13	note based model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	30

4.14	note based model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	31
4.15	note based model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves	32
4.16	note based model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves	33
4.17	note based model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves	34
4.18	note based model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	35
4.19	note based model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	36
4.20	note based model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	37
4.21	simplified note model, hts engine: pitch curves	38
4.22	simplified note model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	39
4.23	simplified note model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	40
4.24	simplified note model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	41
4.25	simplified note model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves	42
4.26	simplified note model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves	43
4.27	simplified note model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves	44
4.28	simplified note model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves	45
4.29	simplified note model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves	46
4.30	simplified note model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves	47

List of Tables

3.1	Phonetic based model label format	11
3.2	Note based model label format	12
4.1	phoneme based model durations	26
4.2	note based model durations	27
4.3	note based simple model durations	27

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Voice synthesis

The voice is a fascinating instrument and the attempts of man to produce it artificially are previous to the appearance of computers and even electricity. In the late nineteenth century, Kempelen built a mechanical synthesizer, considered the first speech synthesizer. In the 20's Leo Theremin developed the first electric synthesizer known, and by the end of the 30's first appeared singing voice synthesizer: the vocoder (Voice Coder) of Dudley. [Siivola, 2002]

There are many ways to synthesize voice, which can be grouped into two main groups: physical models and spectral models. The physical models synthesize voice by building models of the elements involved in phonation: the source or excitation and vocal tract that acts as a filter. [Cornut, 1999] Spectral models attempt to model the spectrum produced by a singer [Sundberg, 1987]. In this case is not intended to mimic the process of sound production, but the resulting sound itself. Within this group are particularly important methods based on a corpus: working directly with the samples or by using a statistical approach.

The methods that work with samples can synthesize speech with great quality, such as unit selection [Hunt and Black, 1996]. These voices, however, require a huge volume of data for training and have little flexibility when handling the samples, this is especially critical in the synthesis of singing voice. In recent years, however, much has

been achieved in this respect [Bonada and Serra, 2007] and have a good example with Vocaloid, developed by the Music Technology Group (UPF) and Yamaha [Bonada, 2008].

On the other hand, statistical methods, such as speech synthesis with hidden Markov models (HMM) [Yoshimura et al., 1999], using a vocoder. That produces a certain buzz in the sound generated. In contrast, however, have great advantages: the voices are stable, with smooth transitions, and their characteristics can be modified easily by transforming HMM parameters appropriately. In recent years HMM speech synthesis has been extended to the singing voice [Oura et al., 2010].

From this and other studies has emerged the HMM-based Singing Voice Synthesis System (Sinsy).

1.2 Style modelling

In the last years, the aim of improving the expressivity of the synthesized voice has lead to the development of a specific research area inside speech and singing technologies: emotional synthesis and style modelling. Thus, the goal is to develop systems that try to capture and reproduce the nuances of the voice.

[Tachibana et al., 2005] presented one of the most important works in the emotional speech synthesis field. In this research, different styles (neutral, sad, rough and joyful) are modelled by HMMs, so each style has its own model as an independent HMM-based voice. Intermediate styles can be also synthesized by applying interpolation between two styles, or a style and neutral. This master thesis has been developed adapting this framework.

Style modelling can be also extended to singing voice synthesis as in [Saino et al., 2010]. Melody (base melody and vibrato) and dynamics are modelled by context dependent HMMs. The system is phoneme independent, so it only takes into account the musical context (notes, durations, etc.). From the trained model can be obtained the synthesis parameters needed by Vocaloid.

1.3 Rap-style singing voice synthesis

Recently, Yamaha and Nagoya Institute of Technologies (NITECH) have presented a Rap-style Singing Voice Synthesis, over Sinsy [Saino et al., 2012]. A statistical approach based on HMMs has been used to model a Japanese rap singer. The input of the system is a rap style musical score defined taking into account the particular characteristics of the modelled singer (Figure 1.1).

From the trained model can be synthesized rap by using the HMM-based singing synthesis system Sinsy. The model also allows to obtain the pitch, gain and phoneme durations and apply them to Vocaloid 3.

Figure 1.1: Yamaha rap synthesis score

Chapter 2

RAP SYNTHESIS IN VOCALOID

The first goal, before generating any model is trying to synthesize rap in Vocaloid by using the parameters extracted from the original recordings. So, this chapter describes this process.

Figure 2.1: Neo during the recording session

2.1 Analysis

This section describes the recording of the rap singer and how this material has been processed.

2.1.1 Recording and processing

Neo, a rap singer from Cornellà has been recorded. He has been asked to perform some of his themes over some instrumentals. The tempo range is between 90 and 135bpm.

The recording has been done using a Neumann U87A. The material recorded consists on 6 themes. The recordings have been normalized and the breaths muted. The phrases have been marked to cut them after.

Figure 2.2: Manual phonetic alignment in Wavesurfer

2.1.2 Phonetic transcription and segmentation

The lyrics have been manually transcribed from the recordings. The phonetic transcription has been done applying rule transcription scripts, and mapped to the Vocaloid

phoneset. The phonetic initial segmentation assigns the same duration to all the phonemes. After that, automatic segmentation has been done by HMM, with the Julius tool. Finally, manual phonetic alignment has been applied in Wavesurfer. An alternative syllable alignment has been implemented. In this strategy the phonemes and their durations are clustered into syllables.

2.1.3 Pitch extraction

The pitch curves have been extracted applying sac analysis in SMSTools. The f0 range has been adjusted in order to avoid octave errors in the detection process. Finally the continuous pitch option has been applied to obtain a continuous curve.

Figure 2.3: Pitch extraction in SMSTools

2.2 Resynthesis

Once the recordings have been done, edited and analysed, the parameters extracted must be processed to apply them to Vocaloid.

Figure 2.4: Vocaloid rap resynthesis process

2.2.1 Vocaloid score

The Vocaloid input is an xml file based format named vsqx. This file contains the notes, with their durations and phonemes. Vsqx allows also including other information expressed as points of a curve: velocity, dynamics, pitch bend, etc. From the .lab file we have obtained from manual phonetic alignment, the notes can be generated. The pitch curves can be formatted as the pitch bend information. The Vocaloid score generation is done by a perl script written by Merlijn Blaauw.

2.2.2 Phonetic alignment and note alignment

There are two ways of alignment that can be applied in the Vocaloid score building. In phonetic alignment there is one note for each phoneme, so the duration of each synthesized phoneme will be the same as in the recording. In note alignment the phonemes are joined in syllables, so there is one note per syllable. The durations of the phonemes can vary compared to the original ones. Vocaloid synthesizes the consonants with their original duration, and adapts the vowels to fit the note duration.

2.2.3 Results

The process described before has been applied in order to study how the rap synthesis work in Vocaloid. The same theme has been synthesized with phonetic alignment and note alignment to compare the two methods. With phonetic alignment, the duration of the consonants is taken into account, so their rhythmic effect is preserved. On the other hand if Vocaloid has to synthesize a consonant larger than the database sample, it applies time stretching. This can cause artefacts. Note alignment has better quality but the rhythmic sense of the consonants is slightly smoothed. However, the differences are not very important because we are dealing with fast tempos.

Chapter 3

MODELLING

Two different models have been built: one phonetic based and another note based. In the phonetic based model the fundamental unit is the phoneme, as in the hmm-based speech original system. In the note based one, the pitch and the durations are modelled for each note.

3.1 Symbolic input and parameters

In speech synthesis all the information is contained in the text, but rap is not only text. Rap is characterized by a musical basis with measures of 4 beats, and the lyrics distributed in this structure. This is often represented in the flow diagram (Figure 3.1).

1	2	3	4
Let me freak the	funk, obso-	lete is the	punk that talks
more junk than	Sanford sells.	I jet pro-	pel at a
rate that compli-	cate their mental	state as I	invade their
masquerade.	They couldn't	fade with a	clipper . . .

Figure 3.1: Example of a flow diagram

3.1.1 Input format

Thus, a symbolic representation of the input is needed. This representation should include the lyrics and how the MC distributes them inside the beat.

The raw text is edited to obtain a sentence per line, and between paragraphs an empty line is inserted. From this orthographic representation, applying the phonetic transcription a sampa representation is obtained. This phonetic format is very useful because includes syllabic divisions. In fact, it is very usual to divide a word between two different beats. Another great advantage is the possibility of transcribing phonetic phenomena as elisions. The flow information is also included by introducing the beat numbers, the silences and the ties (notes that start in a beat and finish in another). The figure 3.2 shows an excerpt of an input.

```
(1) [" f a k] [d e] [" f e I m] {Tie}
(2) {Tie} [" f a k] [d e] (3) [" g e I m]
[" f a k] [m i (4) " t o . m a . n o s]
[m]_[" e] {Tie} (1) {Tie} [" k r j . a o] [a (2) " k i] [r r o . D e (3) " a o] [d e] [t o G . s i (4) " k o . m a . n o s] {Sil}

(1) [" m a . D r e] [p r e o . k u (2) " p a . D a s] [a . s o (3) " m a n . d o . s]_[" a l] [b a l (4) " k o n] {Sil}
[d o n . d e] (1) [" b r u s] [e s (2) " p r i n . t i n] {Sil}
(3) [" n o]_[" e s] [k a . m a (4) " r o n] {Sil}
```

Figure 3.2: Input symbolic representation

3.1.2 Label format

In order to train an HMM model a label format has to be defined. The lab format defined by Zen for HMM-based speech synthesis in English is a good starting point [Zen, 2006].

In the phonetic based model the information related to the flow is added to the original label format (see table 3.1). The note based model follows the same format, but there is only a label for each note (see table 3.2).

3.1.3 Label generation

The original script generates the labels from the text file. This file is phonetically transcribed to XSampa format, and from this transcription all the information needed by the labels is extracted.

p1^ p2-p3+p4=p5 @p6.p7
/A:a1_a2_a3 /B:b1-b2-b3 @b4-b5 &b6-b7 #b8-b9 \$b10-b11 !b12-b13 ;b14-b15 |b16 /C:c1+c2+c3
/D:d1_d2 /E:e1+e2 @e3+e4 &e5+e6 #e7+e8 /F:f1_f2
/G:g1_g2 /H:h1=h2 @h3=h4 |h5 /I:i1_i2
/J:j1+j2-j3
/K:k1+k2-k3 /L:l1+12-13 @l4+l5 /M:m1+m2-m3
/Q:q1 /R:r1 /S:s1

p1	the phoneme identity before the previous phoneme
p2	the previous phoneme identity
p3	the current phoneme identity
p4	the next phoneme identity
p5	the phoneme after the next phoneme identity
p6	position of the current phoneme identity in the current syllable (forward)
p7	position of the current phoneme identity in the current syllable (backward)

a1	whether the previous syllable stressed or not (0: not stressed, 1: stressed)
a2	whether the previous syllable accented or not (0: not accented, 1: accented)
a3	the number of phonemes in the previous syllable

b1	whether the current syllable stressed or not (0: not stressed, 1: stressed)
b2	whether the current syllable accented or not (0: not accented, 1: accented)
b3	the number of phonemes in the current syllable
b4	position of the current syllable in the current word (forward)
b5	position of the current syllable in the current word (backward)
b6	position of the current syllable in the current phrase (forward)
b7	position of the current syllable in the current phrase (backward)
b8	the number of stressed syllables before the current syllable in the current phrase
b9	the number of stressed syllables after the current syllable in the current phrase
b10	the number of accented syllables before the current syllable in the current phrase
b11	the number of accented syllables after the current syllable in the current phrase
b12	the number of syllables from the previous stressed syllable to the current syllable
b13	the number of syllables from the current syllable to the next stressed syllable
b14	the number of syllables from the previous accented syllable to the current syllable
b15	the number of syllables from the current syllable to the next accented syllable
b16	name of the vowel of the current syllable

c1	whether the next syllable stressed or not (0: not stressed, 1: stressed)
c2	whether the next syllable accented or not (0: not accented, 1: accented)
c3	the number of phonemes in the next syllable

d1	gpos (guess part-of-speech) of the previous word
d2	the number of syllables in the previous word

e1	gpos (guess part-of-speech) of the current word
e2	the number of syllables in the current word
e3	position of the current word in the current phrase (forward)
e4	position of the current word in the current phrase (backward)
e5	the number of content words before the current word in the current phrase
e6	the number of content words after the current word in the current phrase
e7	the number of words from the previous content word to the current word
e8	the number of words from the current word to the next content word

f1	gpos (guess part-of-speech) of the next word
f2	the number of syllables in the next word

g1	the number of syllables in the previous phrase
g2	the number of words in the previous phrase

h1	the number of syllables in the current phrase
h2	the number of words in the current phrase
h3	position of the current phrase in utterance (forward)
h4	position of the current phrase in utterance (backward)
h5	TOBI endtone of the current phrase

i1	the number of syllables in the next phrase
i2	the number of words in the next phrase

j1	the number of syllables in this utterance
j2	the number of words in this utterance
j3	the number of phrases in this utterance

k1	whether the previous note is a silence or not (0,1)
k2	whether the previous note is tied or not (0,1)
k3	beat of the previous note

l1	whether the current note is a silence or not (0,1)
l2	whether the current note is tied or not (0,1)
l3	beat of the current note
l4	position of current note in current beat (forward)
l5	position of current note in current beat (backward)

m1	whether the next note is silence or not (0,1)
m2	whether the next note is tied or not (0,1)
m3	beat of the next note

q1	number of notes in the previous beat
r1	number of notes in the current beat
s1	number of notes in the next beat

Table 3.1: Phonetic based model label format

p1-p2+p3	
/A:a1_a2_a3 /B:b1-b2-b3 @b4-b5 &b6-b7 #b8-b9 \$b10-b11 !b12-b13 ;b14-b15 b16 /C:c1+c2+c3	
/D:d1_d2 /E:e1+e2 @e3+e4 &e5+e6 #e7+e8 /F:f1_f2	
/G:g1_g2 /H:h1=h2 @h3=h4 h5 /I:i1_i2	
/J: j1+j2-j3	
/K:k1+k2-k3 /L:l1+l2-l3 @l4+l5 /M:m1+m2-m3	
/Q:q1 /R:r1 /S:s1	
p1	the previous note identity
p2	the current note identity
p3	the next note identity
...	...

Table 3.2: Note based model label format

The adapted script needs two inputs: the text and the XSampa transcription revised to match the MC's performance with the flow info (bits, silences and ties). The text is only used to extract the part-of-speech(pos) information. From the phonetic enriched transcription is extracted the phonetic and the flow related information.

3.2 HMM training

Figure 3.3: General view of the HTS system

The HMM training is based on the Tachibana models [Tachibana et al., 2005]. These models correspond to the HTS system [Zen et al., 2007]. The figure 3.3 shows the training and the synthesis flow diagram.

In the training the spectrum and excitation are modelled by HMMs. The HMMs have state duration distributions that model the speech temporal structure. HMM context dependent are used in order to capture the acoustic variations of the spectrum, pitch and durations, associated to the contextual factors (phonemes, accents, part-of-speech, positions, etc.) In the synthesis, the text to be synthesized is transformed to a context label sequence. From this sequence an HMM sentence is built by concatenating HMMs. From this models the mel-cepstra, log F0 and durations are obtained and applied to a MLSA (Mel Log Spectrum Approximation) filter to synthesize speech. In this project the parameters are used to create a Vocaloid score, so there is no MLSA filter.

3.2.1 Tree-based clustering

Figure 3.4: Decision trees
[Yoshimura, 2002]

When a big number of context factors is involved, the number of possible combinations is huge. But the available data for the training is limited, so it is hard to model

the parameters with precision. To solve this problem, a tree-based context clustering technique is applied to the spectrum, pitch and state duration distributions.

The decision trees are built from the training data by applying questions. Then, the questions link the label fields content with the model. So, the questions file has been adapted to the label format defined to take into account the flow related information.

In the note based strategy, two different models have been trained using different questions files. One, applying phonetic questions related to syllable, word, phrase and utterance information; and another (that we will know as note based simple model) that only takes into account phrase and utterance phonetic information.

3.3 Vocaloid score generation

A new label generation script has been developed, based on the existing speech based one. By applying it to a flow enriched phonetic input, the features context labels will be obtained. These labels allow to retrieve the pitch curve, and the phonetic or note timing from the trained model. Merlijn Blaauw script for vsqx score generation has been adapted to the new environment. This script processes the pitch curve and the segmentation files (phoneme or note, and timings), and transcribes them into Vocaloid notes plus a pitch bend curve.

Chapter 4

RESULTS

Three HMM based models have been generated: one phonetic based, that extends the original speech model adding the flow related information, and two note based, where the durations and the pitch curve are associated to each note. Of each one these models, we have four different subtypes: the hts engine based, one mixture (1mix), semi-tied covariance matrix(stc) and two mixtures (2mix). Moreover, there are three different types of parameter generation (only for 1mix, 2mix and stc). For more details see [Tokuda et al., 2000].

To do an objective evaluation of the results, the differences between the generated durations and the original ones have been computed. On the other hand the generated and the original pitch curves have been plotted to compare them.

4.1 Phonetic based model

In the phonetic based model, the smallest unit is the monophone. The main advantage of this model is that the duration of each phoneme can be modelled individually. As the mel-cepstra information is intimately linked to each phoneme, it can be trained and after recovered allowing speech synthesis by using the hts engine.

The following figures show the pitch curves obtained with the different HMM sub-models. Even though there are slightly differences between them, in general the generated curves are pretty similar to the original ones, but a bit smoothed.

Figure 4.1: phoneme based model, hts engine: pitch curves

Figure 4.2: phoneme based model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.3: phoneme based model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.4: phoneme based model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.5: phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.6: phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.7: phoneme based model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.8: phoneme based model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.9: phoneme based model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.10: phoneme based model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

		Phoneme			Silence		
		correct [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]	dur [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]
hts engine		51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.86	57.78
1mix	0	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.86	57.78
	1	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.86	57.78
	2	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.86	57.78
stc	0	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.58	57.47
	1	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.58	57.47
	2	51.00	25.24	16.53	17.00	51.58	57.47
2mix	0	52.00	25.40	16.64	17.00	51.86	57.78
	1	52.00	25.40	16.64	17.00	51.86	57.78
	2	52.00	25.40	16.64	17.00	51.86	57.78

Table 4.1: phoneme based model durations

As can be observed in the table 4.1, the precision of the obtained durations is almost the same in the different methods, and it must be improved specially with the silences.

4.2 Note based model

In this model the smallest unit has to be defined. In a first attempt two different units were defined: a note and a silence, but the HMM training was impossible because a minimum number of basic elements are needed. Thus, there are three basic types: note, silence note and silence (much shorter). The subtypes are defined according to the number of notes in the beat and the position of the current note in the beat, as well as if the note is tied or not. This model does not allow to define the individual duration of each phoneme but is much more flexible because it is independent of the phonetic content.

By modifying the questions file two different note based model have been built : one taking into account the syllable related information (e.g. accents) and another that only uses part-of-speech, phrase tags and the flow related parameters. The second one is simpler and more similar to the real performance. The rhythmic accentuation imposed by the beat usually match the phonetic accents, but if there are differences, the position of the text inside the beat is more important than the original accents.

		Note			Silence		
		correct [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]	dur [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]
hts engine		46.00	26.90	43.57	25.00	46.51	51.82
1mix	0	46.00	26.90	43.57	25.00	46.51	51.82
	1	46.00	26.90	43.57	25.00	46.51	51.82
	2	46.00	26.90	43.57	25.00	46.51	51.82
stc	0	47.00	26.91	43.59	25.00	46.23	51.51
	1	47.00	26.91	43.59	25.00	46.23	51.51
	2	47.00	26.91	43.59	25.00	46.23	51.51
2mix	0	45.00	26.82	43.44	23.00	47.81	53.27
	1	45.00	26.82	43.44	23.00	47.81	53.27
	2	45.00	26.82	43.44	23.00	47.81	53.27

Table 4.2: note based model durations

The duration model performs pretty well for the notes, but not for the silences.

		Note			Silence		
		correct [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]	dur [%]	diff [%]	diff [ms]
hts engine		43.00	27.38	44.35	12.00	52.99	59.04
1mix	0	43.00	27.39	44.37	16.00	52.51	58.51
	1	43.00	27.39	44.37	16.00	52.51	58.51
	2	43.00	27.39	44.37	16.00	52.51	58.51
stc	0	43.00	27.32	44.25	16.00	52.61	58.61
	1	43.00	27.32	44.25	16.00	52.61	58.61
	2	43.00	27.32	44.25	16.00	52.61	58.61
2mix	0	44.00	27.27	44.18	16.00	53.17	59.23
	1	44.00	27.27	44.18	16.00	53.17	59.23
	2	44.00	27.27	44.18	16.00	53.17	59.23

Table 4.3: note based simple model durations

Figure 4.11: note based model, hts engine: pitch curves

Figure 4.12: note based model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.13: note based model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.14: note based model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.15: note based model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.16: note based model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.17: note based model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.18: note based model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.19: note based model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.20: note based model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.21: simplified note model, hts engine: pitch curves

Figure 4.22: simplified note model, 1mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.23: simplified note model, 1mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.24: simplified note model, 1mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.25: simplified note model, stc, pgtype 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.26: simplified note model, stc, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.27: simplified note model, stc, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Figure 4.28: simplified note model, 2mix, param. gen. type 0: pitch curves

Figure 4.29: simplified note model, 2mix, pgtype 1: pitch curves

Figure 4.30: simplified note model, 2mix, pgtype 2: pitch curves

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

From the analysis/synthesis strategy described in the first chapter can be concluded that rap can be synthesized in Vocaloid with a standard voice obtaining pretty good results. For sure, it could be enhanced by creating a specific Vocaloid rap singer voice. But the main point is to know that Rapaloid it is feasible goal.

Then the main problem is to define a performance model that taught rap to Vocaloid. An input format that includes phonetics and flow info has been proposed, and a context label format adapted to it has been defined. The label generation process has been automatized in order to make training and synthesis easier. Inspired by Tachibana and Makoto HMM based speech framework, two different models have been built. From these and the input lyrics (xsampa transcription with the flow information), Vocaloid vsqx scores can be generated.

The next step should be performing subjective tests. Mean opinion score (MOS) is a very useful and one of the most used strategies. From the results it could be possible to analyse what should be improved and how.

The chosen strategy, close to speech, opens the possibility of automatic generation of flow diagrams from raw text, that is an automatized text to rap system.

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